

Improving Traffic and Transportation at The Technical University of Denmark

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INTRODUCTION

The Technical University of Denmark is the largest technical university in Denmark. With 14.000 people commuting to Lyngby Campus it is crucial for the transportation network to function at its best. At present the public transport to and from DTU is far from perfect, therefore it is important to optimize the transportation to, and on DTU Campus. As Denmark and DTU are the frontrunners of green technology in Europe the image as a green and accessible University is important.

RESEARCH

This project looks at how the transportation from and to DTU could be improved, so that more people either use public transport or their bicycle in an attempt to become greener. Furthermore the project investigates how travelling within the campus could be improved to save travel time, improve safety and generally make it more appealing to move around on campus. Lastly the project looks at how the city centre and surrounding areas are used, and how the students and employees could benefit more from the facilities offered.

METHOD

Data is collected through a quantitative survey sent out to all the student and employees at DTU. The survey is put up on 'Portalen' and is sent out to personal email addresses. A site analysis has also been completed focusing mainly on the DTU campus, where improvements to the transportation possibilities and safety have been discussed.

IDEAS

The central thesis is to create a more open campus, with more room for cycling and improved routes between the four blocks. This is achieved by making more space for bicycle parking or better bike paths. Another way to open up the campus is to create more access points between the blocks.

There are plans to build a light rail through Lyngby with a possibility of it reaching DTU. This has also been researched and it has been discussed how this would affect the transportation possibilities for the student and employees. The light rail would also become a major asset for the further cooperation between Lyngby campus and Ballerup campus.

RESULTS

As the results depend on the survey, we cannot present any since the survey has yet to be answered. However, it is expected that the results will show several methods in which to improve the mobility both internally and externally at DTU.